

Demographic Progression in the Zlin Region

Z. Charvat

Abstract—This paper considers the Zlin region in terms of the demographic conditions of the region - in particular the residential structure and the educational background of the inhabitants. The paper also considers migration of the population within the Zlin region. Migration is of importance in terms of conservation of the working potential of the region.

Keywords—Demographic structure, migration, inhabitants, residential structure, age structure, learning structure, Zlin region.

I. INTRODUCTION

FROM contemporary look of the demographic development of the region there is a change of owing to bad structure of inhabitants to dullness natural accession of inhabitants. In the two last years there is a change of mild growth population curve, because of the grow of population tie strong form of year 70-ties. Another important factor is that in the Zlin Region is very bad infrastructure; it faces to the brawn drain of inhabitants and similarly bring down natural accession of inhabitants. This situation is reflected in the article and it could be refer to on feasible solution resource from this situation, which however requires deeper analyses. Farther in the article there is a deeper analysis of cultural structure of inhabitants and it is from 1991 and 2001 when was the last population census.

II. AIM AND METHODS

Aim of this paper is to learn what is the demographic situation in the Zlin Region between the years 2000-2005. As methods of this paper was adopted analysis of sources of information and quantitative analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic is social science which subject is phenomenon and suit, let us say, regularity that have this phenomenon and suit control over. Demographic phenomenon and suit are those which are relate to people reproduction or exactly with human reproduction, be alive to accurate as partly renewal loom inhabitant through the medium biosocial suit of natality and mortality and partly as general renewal inhabitants, include of renewal inhabitant migrate.

A. Resident Structure

Majerova contextualize that resident structure is lay out inhabitant to the single seat that are seat of insider Living building, and single resident.

The Zlin Region was established in 1. 1. 2000 as one of the 14 regions of the territory of the Czech Republic. It is divided to the 4 district - Kromeriz, Uherske Hradiste, Vsetin and

Zlin.

The Zlin Region is with his surface 3963 km² rank only 5 % surface of the Czech Republic, and it is eleventh region of its size.

B. Age Bracket and Mortality

Population of the Zlin Region becomes still older. From the year 2000 to the 2005 was bringing down portion.

Youngest age bracket 0 - 14 year influence decreasing measure birth rate from 16,2 % to the 14,7 %. The biggest decreasing was at age category of 6 - 14 years. In result expressive fall in natality of nineties years.

Portion people alive in age bracket (15 - 64 years), is between years 2000 - 2005 intensify about 0,7 %. In economic view is probably going about favourable structure of inhabitants, because in alive age are the biggest demographic years, of the population groundswell (50.and 70 years).

The biggest run was between age bracket 25 - 34 years (1,1 %) and between 55 - 64 years (1,6 %) The run of the portion people ahead pension age evokes needs developments lifetime edify older generation, to be keeping working potential.

Fig. 1 Age structure inhabitant the Zlin region in years 2000 - 2005

TABLE I
 MORTALITY AFTER GENDER AND AGE [5]

	2000					2001					2002					2003					2004					2005					Index 2005/2000																																																																														
	Total dead					Dead on 1000 inhabitants					Dead on 1000 men					in age: 15 - 29 years					30 - 49 years					50 - 59 years						60 - 69 years					70 and more years																																																																								
70 and more years	63,4	63,9	63,9	64,4	59,8	60,8	61,72	60,16	58,55	63,45	59,78	62,65	101,5	10,3	10,1	9,9	10,7	10,1	10,6	10,6	10,3	10,1	10,9	10,6	102,8	11,1	10,6	10,4	11,3	10,9	11,5	103,2	0,9	0,9	1	0,8	1	1	115,2	3,7	3,3	3,2	3,1	3,1	3,2	87,1	12,1	11,7	10,4	12,7	11,7	12,1	99,4	29,1	25,6	25,7	23,6	25,2	24,3	83,5	83,7	80,6	77,5	85,8	76,7	83,1	99,4	9,6	9,6	9,3	10,2	9,4	9,8	102,5	0,4	0,3	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,5	122,8	1,2	1,3	1,3	1,3	1	1,2	100,5	4,5	4	4	4,9	3,4	4	88	11,6	10,7	11	10,7	9,5	9,5	82,3	63,4	63,9	63,9	64,4	59,8	60,8	95,9

C. Dead People on 1000 Inhabitants

In period under consideration at the Zlin Region was death more people than was children natality. It has natural decrease effect inhabitants in the Zlin Region. Number of dead people on 1000 inhabitants was as far as 2004 in the Zlin Region than in the Czech Republic. In 2005 it was gently upper the Czech Republic average.

D. Learning Structure

One of the sources of information about achieved level of the culture is data obtained from regularly decennary cycle population census.

Compared to the year 1991 was in the year 2001 in the Zlin Region higher portion inhabitants with secondary school and graduation including higher and it was about 5,8 %.

Number of people with only basic school was going down from 35,3 % in 1991 to the 24,8% in 2001. Highest % in the Zlin Region has apprentice culture and high school without graduation (39,0 %).

In 2001 was number of people with university 38 104 what was 7,7 % of inhabitants.

Mostly substitution group of men was without graduation and with apprentice culture. Their portion was from 1991 going up about 2,1%. Yet markedly was growing up portion men with high school, with graduation including higher, and it was from 20,3 % in 1991 to the 24,6 % in 2001.

By the women in the Zlin Region it was most groups with basic culture including without finishing. In the 1991 was their portion about 44,9 % its one half. In 2001 tailed off women portion with basic culture to 32,6 %. About 7,3 % was going up portion with high school and graduation, compared to 1991. In the Zlin Region have more women High school with graduation than men. [5]

E. Migration

From 2001 to the 2004 it was turn out in the Zlin Region more person than was move in. Balance of migration has negative worth; at 2004 was decrease of inhabitants highest from 1990. In 2005 was balance migration positive. To the Zlin Region was move in 31 person, than was turn out.

Portion move in to the Zlin Region was from 2000 to the 2003 going up, from 2004 was declined. At 2005 was move in 3510 person, from that 1019 was from foreign country. Generally was from 2000 to the 2005 move in to the Zlin Region 22 475 person. More than 55 % of all were men.

Most of move in (mainly foreign Citizen) incoming to the region for work, what relate to increasing portion move in working age (73,1 % in year 2000, 79,8 % in year 2005).

Number of move in children to the region was to 2003 decreasing, from 2003 where mount up. From 2005 was 16,5 % move in age 0 – 14 years. Rate of people older than 65 years has declined.

While 2003 was 46,4 % of all move in to the region from foreign country, at 2005 their portion bring down on 29,0 %. Between move in from inland was in 2004 mostly people with secondary school and graduation 35,7 %, at once behind then 34 % frame move in with secondary school without graduation, and 14,8 % move in has university education. [5]

IV. CONCLUSION

In this article was outlined situation from 90-ties to present, as migration situation, but also as culture structure population. This analysis ascertain that person who were move in from foreign country are coming for better job.

Next ascertainment was that in the Region Zlin grow up slowly number of person with secondary school, but almost graduated. It supposes that this situation will be better. Uses data was ascertain of regular cycles of population census.

TABLE II
INHABITANTS IN AGE 15 AND MORE YEARS

	2000		2001		2002		2003		2004		2005		Total 2000 - 2005
	number	%											
Hyp herated to tal	2967		3463		4216		4348		3972		3510		22476
of women	1555		1651		1834		1736		1674		1644		10094
From total in age:													
0 - 15 years	193		225		199		189		205		240		1251
6 - 14 years	346		337		363		296		294		340		1976
15 - 18 years	159		178		200		282		200		175		1194
19 - 24 years	496		576		681		834		667		437		3691
25 - 34 years	800		938		1210		1240		1189		1062		6439
35 - 44 years	332		462		676		611		601		532		3214
45 - 54 years	205		312		438		507		405		344		2211
55 - 64 years	176		219		212		188		222		174		1191
65 and more years	260		216		237		201		189		206		1309

ACCORDANCE gender and highest finished learning structure (SLDB) [5]

TABLE III
MOVE IN PORTION GENDER AND AGE [5]

	Total		Men		Women	
	number	%	number	%	number	%
Inhabitants in age 15 and more years	1991	467271	100	224580	100	242691
	2001	496595	100	239609	100	986
With the education:						
Primary education not finished	1991	164899	35,3	56036	25	108863
Apprentice and secondary school	2001	123193	24,8	39477	16,5	83716
Education without graduation	1991	170258	36,4	103595	46,1	66663
	2001	193818	39	115473	48,2	78345
Secondary school with graduation including higher education	1991	100352	21,5	45680	20,3	54672
	2001	135488	27,3	58953	24,6	76535
University education	1991	27523	5,9	17583	7,8	9940
	2001	38104	7,7	22819	9,5	15285
						6

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Koschin, Demography for the first time. Prague: Oeconomica, 2005.
- [2] F. Koschin, Chapter from the economic demography. Prague: Oeconomica, 2005.
- [3] V. Majerova at al., Sociology of the country and the agricultural. Prague: University of life sciences in Prague, 2003.
- [4] V. Roubicek: Introduction into the demography. Prague: Codex Bohemia, 1997.
- [5] Czech statistics office, "Statistical date (Unpublished work style)" unpublished.